

HeriTACE

HeriTACE Visual Identity

Deliverable D7.2

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Project information

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Project Title	Future-proofing Heritage Townhouses by Optimising Comfort and Energy in Time and Space
Project Acronym	HeriTACE
Project Coordinator	Arnold Janssens, Ghent University
Project Duration	1 January 2024 - 31 December 2027 (48 months)

Deliverable information

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Lead Organisation	LGI
Contributing Partner(s)	ACE
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Visual Identity

All the communication and dissemination tools described in this deliverable are consistent with the HeriTACE project's brand identity, which aligns with the image that the project wishes to convey.

In addition, all materials, including scientific papers and publications produced by the project, must acknowledge EU support, and display the EU emblem (figure 1) and funding statement (Article 17.2). Moreover, it is important to note that "when displayed in association with other logos, the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos" (Article 17.2).

Figure 1: EU emblem

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The different channels and tools presented in this section will be further developed in D7.1.

1. Logo

One of the first communications actions (Task 7.2) was to develop the visual identity of the project. It is, and will be, associated and included in all paper and electronic documentation, as well as in all promotional materials.

To build its brand recognition from the very beginning, a first version of the logo was designed for the HeriTACE kick-off meeting. To ensure a strong project identity, several logo versions were designed, analysed and edited afterwards, to best represent HeriTACE in the simplest and clearest way possible.

The final version of the HeriTACE logo features a creative logo mark and a bold typeface to make a lasting impression on viewers and ensure project visibility. The logo mark consists of townhouses buildings surrounded by a circle representing the holistic model. The typeface presents the project name in clear, distinct letters, enabling the logo to stand out on all electronic or printed materials. Several other logo options were designed to offer versatility.

Figure 2: Official logo

Figure 3: Logo variations

1.2. Rules when using the logo

When using the logo, the following rules apply:

- It cannot be modified and must be used on all promotional materials (paper or electronic) related to or produced during the project
- The HeriTACE logo must be used in PNG format with a transparent background, or in EPS format (vector option, high definition for printed documents, goodies...)
- All versions of the logo are available for download on the collaborative project workspace
- When used with other logos, the HeriTACE logo size must be proportional to that of other logos
- For optimal visibility, accessibility and readability, the logo must be surrounded by a proportional amount of blank space as illustrated below

Figure 4: Incorrect and correct uses of the EDAPHOS logo

1.3. Logotype

One typeface was selected for the project logo. The choice was made based on its readability and structure, which provides a clear, distinct, and appealing image.

The project title "HeriTACE" uses Ginóra Sans.

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz123456789

These fonts cannot be modified and must be used for the HeriTACE logo. Although these are the logotype font, they do not have to be used in cover, body copy or official correspondence.

1.4. Colour palette

To illustrate the heritage and restoration aspects of the project, a palette going from royal blue to yellow was used, representing heat and cold flows.

Figure 5: Colour Palette

1.5. Typefaces

The typefaces to be used in documents such as Word, PowerPoint and other desktop applications should be:

- Ginora Sans for headers and titles:

**abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 123456789?.,;./!+-@**

- Avenir Next LT Pro for body text:

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxy
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 123456789?.,;./!+-@

2. Project Presentation Templates

A PowerPoint presentation template was designed and distributed to all partners. Easy to use and versatile, the template adds value to the HeriTACE brand and ensures the project's visibility when presented at events or conferences. The consortium partners have been invited to use those templates when it comes to present the project in public events, conferences, etc.

Figure 6: PowerPoint Template

3. Deliverable Templates

A Word document template was also prepared and shared with all HeriTACE partners shortly after the start of the project. Consistent with the HeriTACE visual identity and streamlined for ease of use, the template makes it easy for partners to collaborate on deliverables.

Figure 7: Deliverable Template cover

4. Other materials

Flyer: a flyer has been designed and will be distributed at events, internal or external. It includes key messages, objectives, expected impacts, consortium members and contact information. The flyer will be printed on demand to avoid waste.

Poster: a poster has been designed for display at various events and conferences attended by project partners. It includes visual elements that represent the project, a brief summary, key objectives, consortium members and contact information.

Roll-up: a roll-up has been designed for display at various events and conferences attended by project partners. It includes visual elements that represent the project, a brief summary, consortium members and contact information. The roll-up will only be printed once the first physical event is confirmed.

Other promotional materials: visuals will be created to promote project events, publications and project news across the HeriTACE communication channels including social media as needed. The visual identity of the project will be also incorporated an overview video that will be produced in the upcoming months.